

Total Factor Productivity and Foreign Human Capital: Evidence from the Western Balkans

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ABSTRACT

The Western Balkan Six economies have advanced structural reforms to boost economic growth, create new jobs, and bring living standards closer to those in Europe. However, the Western Balkan residents continue to be encouraged to look for career and educational possibilities outside of the region due to the slow rate of convergence and the significant development gap with other European nations. Over the past ten years, the Western Balkan emigration rate has increased by 10%, and as a result, about one-fifth of the population now lives outside of the region. The high levels of emigration that continue can be extremely challenging for development. They may cause skill shortages and labor market distortions, which may discourage potential investors from making investments because they are unable to find the necessary skills. Gaining competitiveness, attracting investment, and navigating the area's ecological and digital transition all depend on human capital and a competent workforce that can meet the labor market's skill requirements and spur innovation. They are also important pillars of an economy's resilience and prosperity, which is important in light of the COVID-19 pandemic and the changing nature of the global environment. The goal of this paper is to examine how immigrants contribute to innovation in Western Balkans. Using Total Factor Productivity as a measure of innovation. The focus is on the Western Balkan countries (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia). The relationship between migration and innovation is examined not only at regional, but also at sectoral level. This makes it possible to quantify the direct impact of immigrants in the industry where they are really employed. To address the potential endogeneity of migration we adopt instrumental variable technique originally devised by Card (2001). Moreover, we carried out the analysis of human capital composition across sectors in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The offered recommendations can be used by policy makers when designing future policies.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the exploration of migration's relationship with innovation and productivity, the prevailing geographical approach has traditionally dominated scholarly discourse. Grounded in seminal works such as that of Dolado, Goria, and Ichino (1994), this approach typically analyzes the impact of migration on innovation and productivity at the regional or national level, often overlooking the nuances embedded within specific economic sectors. However, this introduction posits that a comprehensive understanding of this relationship necessitates a shift towards a sectoral analysis, an avenue that has been relatively underexplored in the extant literature.

As demonstrated in prior research, the geographic approach tends to explore the innovation performances of entire regions or countries, neglecting the heterogeneity within economic sectors

that play a pivotal role in shaping productivity growth. Technological regimes, as elucidated by Breschi et al. (2000), underscore the importance of sector-specific technologies in influencing rates of productivity growth. Consequently, a nation or region's overall productivity growth becomes a combination of disparate rates within various sectors—rates that may or may not be influenced by immigrant workers. The oversight of this sectoral dimension in previous analyses prompts the adoption of a more nuanced approach, exploring the impact of migration at the sectoral level.

Beyond geographical considerations, this introduction integrates insights from the methodology, incorporating two sets of data to assess the effect of migration on sectoral innovation. The first set emanates from a survey conducted in Bosnia and Herzegovina, focusing on top management, HR, or talent managers within the Construction, IT, and Services sectors. Employing both random and purposive sampling strategies, this survey not only delves into the labor force composition but also serves as a foundational dataset for our sectoral analysis. The second set draws from reputable international organizations, ensuring data compatibility and dependability.

Furthermore, the discussion extends to the direct effects of migrants on innovation and productivity, revealing potential overestimations in studies that adopt a geographical approach. High rates of productivity growth within innovative sectors may attract foreign labor, but the dispersion of immigrant contributions across sectors, including those with limited innovation, necessitates a sectoral lens for accurate assessment. Additionally, the influence of migrants' education levels is examined, emphasizing the importance of considering contributions from both highly skilled and less-educated immigrants across diverse economic activities.

As we embark on this inquiry, our methodological rigor stands out. Rigorous survey design, incorporating power analysis and dual sampling techniques, is coupled with data from esteemed international sources. The validity and reliability of our survey instrument are buttressed by a comprehensive literature review, managerial input, and a pilot test. Employing statistical analyses, including descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis, our study seeks to unravel the intricate dynamics between migration, sectoral innovation, and productivity. This multi-faceted approach positions our research to contribute nuanced insights, addressing the gaps and limitations inherent in the existing literature.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on migration's impact on productivity and innovation spans both macro-level and micro-level analyses. Early work by Dolado, Gorio, and Ichino (1994) introduced migrant labor into aggregate production functions, finding effects of both high- and low-skilled foreign workers on GDP per capita. Since then, numerous country- and region-level studies have examined immigration's influence on various innovation proxies – from patent counts to productivity growth – and many report positive impacts. For example, Ortega and Peri (2014) find that immigration raises total factor productivity (TFP) at the national level. Similarly, Alesina, Harnoss, and Rapoport (2013) document that a higher share of immigrants (especially diverse, highly skilled ones) correlates with greater GDP per capita and TFP across countries. In Europe, Bosetti, Cattaneo, and Verdolini (2015) show that inflows of skilled migrants correspond to more patent applications, and Kerr and Lincoln (2010) find that increases in visas for high-skilled foreigners led to higher patenting in U.S. cities. These macro-level studies suggest that immigration – particularly of highly educated workers – can be a catalyst for innovation and productivity growth in host economies (Dohse and Gold, 2014). A few exceptions exist, however: Bratti and Conti (2014) detect no effect of highly skilled immigrant shares (and even a negative effect of low-skilled shares) on patenting in Italian provinces, indicating that positive immigration-innovation links are not universal. On balance, the broad evidence at the national or regional scale leans positive, with immigration often credited for contributing to technical

progress and growth. Notably, this appears to hold for both high- and lower-skilled migrants in advanced economies, as even less-educated immigrants have been found to raise productivity in some contexts. Such findings underscore the potential economy-wide benefits of foreign human capital, while also hinting at complexities beneath the aggregate level.

In contrast to the generally favorable macro evidence, firm-level and other micro-level studies paint a more nuanced picture. When examining individual companies or plants, results have been mixed and sometimes contradictory. Several studies have failed to find a strong direct effect of employing immigrants on firm innovation outcomes. For instance, analyses of German and Danish firms detected no significant benefits of migrant worker presence or workforce cultural diversity on the likelihood of introducing innovations. Trax, Brunow, and Suedekum (2015) report no productivity gains from a higher share of migrants or more diverse origins at the plant level in Germany, and Østergaard et al. (2011) similarly find no specific advantage of employee ethnic diversity for innovation in Danish firms. Using Dutch firm data, Ozgen, Nijkamp, and Poot (2013) even found a negative relationship between the share of immigrant employees and firm innovativeness (though interestingly a positive relationship for the diversity of national backgrounds). Their later work confirmed that outcomes are sensitive to context: the effect of diversity on innovation varied markedly between Germany and the Netherlands and under different model specifications. On the other hand, there is evidence that under certain conditions migrant diversity can aid firms' creativity – for example, McGuirk and Jordan (2012) showed that Irish regions with more culturally diverse labor pools had a higher probability of firms introducing new products. It is worth noting that in that study diversity was measured at the regional level, not within each firm suggesting spillover effects from a diverse local talent pool. Overall, compared to the macro-level consensus, micro-level research indicates that immigration's impact on innovation is not automatic and can depend on firm-specific or local circumstances. Indeed, a recent multi-country firm study found only selective positive effects: high-skilled non-EU immigrants were on average not associated with higher productivity growth, likely due to skill mismatch (many working in lower-productivity jobs), although some industries did benefit from more such migrants. These mixed findings highlight that the migration-innovation link is complex and may be mediated by how effectively firms and industries utilize foreign talent.

One explanation for the discrepancy between aggregate and firm-level results lies in sectoral heterogeneity. The prevailing approach in the literature has been geographic – analyzing migration effects at the country or regional level. While useful for capturing broad trends, this approach can obscure important differences across economic sectors. Immigrants are not evenly distributed across industries, and industries themselves differ in their innovation patterns. The technological regimes literature emphasizes that each sector follows a distinct innovation trajectory; the rate and nature of productivity growth vary greatly between, say, a high-tech manufacturing industry and a low-tech service field. Broad regional growth often results from a few dynamic sectors, which may or may not employ many immigrants. If a region's booming high-tech firms drive productivity gains and also attract foreign workers, a regional analysis might wrongly attribute the growth to those immigrants as a whole – even if many of them actually work in unrelated, less innovative local industries. In other words, geographic studies risk overestimating migrants' contributions by failing to account for which sectors are generating innovation. A sector-focused approach can isolate the direct impact of migrants within the industries they are employed, thereby offering a clearer picture of causality. Indeed, a key question emerging from prior work is whether the positive effects of immigration on innovation still hold when examined at the industry level rather than in aggregate. Recent evidence suggests that sectoral analysis is fruitful: productivity studies in the Balkans confirm that aggregate TFP trends mask substantial inter-industry variation, reinforcing the importance of disaggregating by sector. By examining sector-specific outcomes, researchers can better determine in which areas of the economy migrant human capital has the greatest impact (Breschi et al., 2000).

Sectoral analysis also allows consideration of different types of innovation and the roles of high- vs. low-skilled migrants. Much of the literature, especially at the macro level, implicitly assumes that highly educated immigrants are the primary drivers of innovation, focusing on outcomes like patents or R&D that heavily rely on advanced skills. Indeed, in science- and technology-intensive sectors, innovation often requires formal research activities and specialized knowledge that high-skilled workers provide. However, innovation is a multifaceted phenomenon that extends beyond just R&D labs. In many medium-tech and low-tech industries, firms innovate through incremental improvements, adoption of existing technologies, or process innovations – for example, acquiring new machinery or refining production techniques. These productivity-enhancing changes might not generate patents, but they do raise efficiency and are captured by TFP growth. Crucially, such improvements do not always require workers with advanced degrees; practical know-how and on-the-job experience can be more important in implementing new processes or equipment. Santamaría et al. (2009) show that firms in low- and mid-tech sectors often innovate “beyond formal R&D” by leveraging employee skills and adaptations on the factory floor. Von Hippel’s classic study (1976) similarly highlighted the role of end-users and production workers in driving innovative improvements from the bottom up. This suggests that immigrants with modest formal education can still contribute meaningfully to innovation in certain settings – for instance, a skilled tradesperson from abroad might introduce new techniques in a construction firm, or migrant service workers might bring ideas that improve customer service processes. Ignoring these contributions by focusing only on highly educated migrants would present an incomplete picture. Moreover, in many countries (including those in the Western Balkans), immigrants tend to be overrepresented in lower-skill jobs. By considering diverse skill levels, sectoral studies can capture the full range of productivity impacts – from top-end scientific innovation to ground-level efficiency gains. In sum, Total Factor Productivity is a particularly useful measure in this context because it reflects broad productivity-enhancing activities, not just formal innovations. TFP growth is often described as “technical progress in its broadest sense” (Solow, 1957), encompassing any improvements in output not explained by labor and capital inputs. This makes it an appropriate metric for sectoral innovation studies, as it will register gains from both R&D-driven breakthroughs and incremental operational improvements. By using TFP as our innovation proxy, we align with a growing literature that treats productivity gains as a comprehensive indicator of innovation performance, suitable for comparing high-tech and low-tech sectors alike.

Another dimension of heterogeneity is the cultural diversity of migrant populations. Beyond the sheer number of immigrants, researchers have asked whether a more diverse pool of national origins stimulates innovation by bringing together varied perspectives. At the aggregate level, several studies answer in the affirmative: greater diversity among immigrants is linked to higher regional productivity and innovation outcomes. For example, Alesina et al. (2013) find that countries with more diverse immigrant communities exhibit higher TFP, especially when that diversity is among skilled workers. Similarly, using European regional data, Özgen, Nijkamp, and Poot (2012) show that regions hosting a mix of nationalities have higher patenting rates. These findings echo management studies on multicultural teams, which often credit diversity with enhancing creative problem-solving (Stahl et al., 2010). The policy implication sometimes drawn is that attracting immigrants from a variety of backgrounds (for instance, via diversity-oriented visa policies) could boost innovation. However, as with total immigrant numbers, a sectoral perspective reveals a more complex reality. One issue is that regional immigrant diversity may proxy for economic diversity. In Europe and elsewhere, immigration tends to occur in waves dominated by certain nationalities, often responding to historical ties or geopolitical events. These waves also tend to fill labor needs in specific industries. For instance, post-war Germany saw successive waves of Italian, then Turkish, then Eastern European migrants, each group concentrating in particular sectors that were expanding at the time. Over time, a country or region with a wide range of industries will naturally host immigrants from many different origins, because each sector draws workers from specific source

countries. In the Western Balkans today, for example, construction, tourism, and agriculture might each attract different migrant groups, yielding diversity at the national level simply as a byproduct of having multiple sectors. It is well known that a diversified economic base itself fosters innovation by allowing knowledge spillovers between industries (Jacobs, 1969; Feldman & Audretsch, 1999). Thus, the positive effect of immigrant diversity observed in cross-region studies could partly reflect the benefits of industry diversity rather than any special creative synergy from multicultural workplaces. A sector-level analysis can disentangle this by examining diversity within industries. If diversity is truly beneficial due to idea recombination among workers of different backgrounds, we would expect to see gains even within a single sector when its workforce is international. On the other hand, if diversity's apparent benefits mostly capture broad economic variety, controlling for sector will diminish those effects. In short, the sectoral approach allows us to separate the "diversity effect" from the confounding influence of diversified regional economies. This nuance is especially relevant for the Western Balkan region, where immigrant diversity is growing in tandem with gradual economic diversification, and needs careful interpretation.

A further factor potentially affecting migration–innovation outcomes is the age structure of migrant vs. native workers. Immigrant labor forces are often younger on average than the domestic workforce. Youth can be an advantage for innovation – younger workers may have more up-to-date training and tend to be more open to new ideas, whereas older workers have experience but could be less flexible or creative. The literature on age and innovation is not entirely settled: while it's generally found that creativity and the propensity to produce radical inventions decline with age (Jones, 2010; Öberg, 1960), other work suggests that peak innovation output can occur after a period of experience accumulation (Schubert & Andersson, 2013). Regardless, if immigrants are disproportionately in their 20s and 30s, whereas the native workforce skews older, part of the innovation impact attributed to migrants might actually be an age effect. A younger workforce (immigrant or not) could simply be more productive and innovative. Failing to account for age differences could therefore confound results. Studies of migration and innovation increasingly recognize this and control for workforce age structure. For our purposes, it is an additional consideration in the Western Balkans, as these countries face aging native populations alongside inflows of younger foreign workers. Any analysis must ensure that we isolate the effect of migration itself from such demographic factors.

When we turn to the Western Balkans, we find a context with unique migration dynamics and a relative dearth of prior research on the topic. The Western Balkan economies (e.g., Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia) are characterized more by emigration than immigration. Over the past decades, a significant share of their population – often the most skilled – has left to seek opportunities abroad. As of recent years, roughly one-fifth of the region's people live outside their country of origin, leading to concerns about brain drain and skill shortages in the local labor markets. This context is quite different from that of Western European countries or the United States, where much of the immigration–innovation literature has focused. In the Western Balkans, the pool of foreign human capital (immigrants) is relatively small and has specific features. Some immigrants are regional (from neighboring countries), while others arrive as asylum seekers or temporary transit migrants (for instance, recent influxes from conflict regions in the Middle East and Ukraine). The educational profile of these arrivals has been mixed – for example, surveys in 2022 indicated that a majority of migrants passing through had only primary or secondary education, although certain refugee groups (such as Ukrainian displaced persons) were highly educated (Figure 1).

Because the Western Balkan states are not traditional migrant magnets, the scale at which foreign workers participate in their economies is modest. This means that evidence from large economies with sizeable immigrant workforces might not directly translate. It also means there has been little scholarly attention to whether and how the limited foreign human capital present in these countries contributes to innovation. Most related studies focus instead on the consequences of emigration

(e.g., loss of human capital and its impact on growth) or on aggregate productivity trends during post-socialist transition. For instance, recent growth accounting analyses have measured TFP improvements in Western Balkan countries, but without explicitly linking these to immigration. The role of incoming migrants in the region’s innovation system thus remains an open question. We lack robust evidence on whether sectors that employ more foreign workers are any more dynamic in terms of productivity. It is also unclear if the generally positive impacts of migration observed elsewhere apply in an environment with different migrant composition and possibly institutional barriers to fully utilizing foreign talent.

Figure 1: Highest level of educational attainment

Source: Migration Trends in the Western Balkans in 2022. IOM’s Displacement Tracking Matrix

The present study seeks to fill this gap in the literature by providing a focused examination of migration and innovation in the Western Balkans at the sectoral level. By using TFP growth as our measure of innovation, we capture a broad range of productivity-enhancing activities – from formal R&D outcomes to informal efficiency gains – which is well-suited to the region’s sectoral context where radical innovation (patenting) is relatively scarce but productivity improvements are vital. We explicitly analyze the relationship between the presence of immigrant workers and TFP across different industries, both to quantify any direct contributions of migrants and to see how effects differ by sector. In doing so, we build on the insights from prior research: our approach accounts for sectoral heterogeneity, distinguishes between skill levels of migrants (high-skilled vs. lower-skilled) as relevant for each sector, and considers origin diversity within sectors. This nuanced treatment allows us to test whether the positive impacts found in aggregate studies hold true in the Western Balkan setting, or whether factors like skill mismatch and small migrant shares yield more muted effects. Importantly, our study is among the first to investigate sector-specific migration–TFP linkages in the Western Balkans, an area previously under-explored. By comparing results across industries, we can identify where foreign human capital matters most – for example, whether technology-intensive sectors reap significant benefits from even a few skilled migrants, or whether services and low-tech manufacturing also see gains from migrant labor through incremental innovation. We also highlight any sectoral gaps where the absence of foreign expertise might be hindering innovation, thus offering insight into where policy interventions (such as attracting certain types of talent) could be most effective. In sum, this literature review has shown that migration can be a driver of innovation and productivity, but the effects are not uniform and depend on the context. The Western Balkans provide a distinctive case to apply these insights. Our study contributes to the literature by extending the migration–innovation analysis to a new regional context with sectoral granularity, helping to clarify whether and how foreign human capital boosts TFP in transitioning economies. This contribution not only addresses a gap in academic knowledge but also has practical implications for Western Balkan policymakers striving to enhance competitiveness through human capital and innovation.

Hypothesis development

This study focused on investigating the relationship between the number of foreign employees and the level of diversity in organizations. We hypothesize that firms with a bigger number of foreign employees have higher diversity level according to their managers.

H1. Companies with higher foreign employees' number have higher level of diversity perception.

This hypothesis suggests a positive relationship between the level of diversity and number of foreign employees.

As we established earlier the overall productivity growth of a nation or region may be the result of very heterogeneous rates of growth in various sectors. Moreover, creative activities can vary greatly among industries and usually call for a wide range of skills. So, we hypothesize that there should be dependency between industry and the type of foreign workers' employment.

H2. Industry can predict the number of foreign employees employed permanently or temporarily.

3. METHODOLOGY

To examine how foreign human capital influences broad productivity-enhancing activities—captured by Total Factor Productivity — across economic sectors in the Western Balkans, we employ a two-pronged, sectorally disaggregated approach. First, we conduct a firm-level survey in Bosnia and Herzegovina to capture micro-level workforce composition, including skill mix, age structure, and cultural diversity. Second, we assemble a panel of secondary data on TFP and migration from international sources for five Western Balkan economies and apply both descriptive and instrumental-variable regressions at the sectoral level. This mixed method design aligns with our literature review's emphasis on TFP as a broad indicator of innovation and productivity-enhancing changes (e.g., process improvements, organizational capital, technology adoption), and on the importance of sectoral heterogeneity, skill levels, age, and diversity.

We selected Bosnia and Herzegovina as a case study because its sectoral structure and recent migration trends mirror those of neighboring Western Balkan states. Focusing on the Construction, Information Technology (IT), and Services sectors—each representing low-, high-, and medium-technology segments respectively—allows us to observe how foreign human capital contributes to TFP-relevant activities across diverse innovation regimes. We targeted senior managers and HR directors (CEOs, HR managers, talent leads) in firms registered with the national business registry. A two-stage strategy ensured representativeness: (1) random sampling from the registry to secure broad coverage, and (2) purposive sampling to guarantee adequate representation of each sector and firm-size category. This yielded 53 complete responses.

The structured questionnaire, administered online over a three-month period in 2021, collected:

1. Number and share of foreign-born employees, disaggregated by contract type (permanent vs. temporary), skill level (tertiary-educated vs. secondary-or-below), and age group (under 35 vs. 36 and older).
2. Managers' perception of national-origin diversity on a 1–5 scale, supplemented by counts of distinct nationalities employed.
3. Firm characteristics: sector, total employment, presence of an R&D department, and overall R&D expenditure adequacy.

To ensure content validity, we (a) reviewed the instrument against our literature synthesis on migration–innovation links, (b) solicited feedback from five practicing managers in each sector, and (c) pilot-tested with five additional firms. Iterative revisions improved clarity and alignment with constructs such as skill mismatch, age effects, and diversity-mediated innovation. We used IBM SPSS for quantitative analysis:

1. Descriptive statistics to profile firm size, sectoral distribution, foreign employee shares, skill composition, age structure, and diversity scores.
2. Pearson correlations examining bivariate links between foreign-born share and diversity, age structure and diversity, and sector dummies with permanent employment of migrants.
3. Ordinary least squares (OLS) regressions to test: Whether the share of foreign-born employees predicts perceived workforce diversity (a proxy for cross-cultural idea recombination). Whether sector membership (dummy-coded) predicts the share of foreign-born workers in permanent roles, reflecting sectoral differences in skill retention.

In all regressions, we controlled for firm size and presence of R&D activity. We checked OLS assumptions—linearity, homoscedasticity, normality, and multicollinearity—and used a stringent significance threshold ($p < .001$) to mitigate false positives given multiple tests and sample size.

The second set of information used in this study came from international organizations, ensuring its compatibility and dependability. Nevertheless, this method has certain drawbacks in that we were unable to provide data for every country for some indicators. Thus, we used data from World Bank’s World Development Indicators, the IMF’s Outlook data base from October 2020, the International Labor Organization (ILO), the World Economic Forum, and Eurostat. Migration indicators included the share of foreign-born in the labor force, migrant skill composition (tertiary-educated share), and measures of origin diversity (fractionalization index), drawn from ILO and WDI databases.

Our methodology directly responds to the literature’s identified needs: it treats TFP as a broad measure of all productivity-enhancing activities (formal innovation, process upgrades, organizational practices) rather than restricting to patent-based metrics. By focusing on sectoral disaggregation, we avoid aggregation bias and can pinpoint where foreign human capital has significant leverage. Inclusion of skill-level, age structure, and diversity measures allows us to test theoretical channels—codified knowledge in high-tech sectors, incremental innovation in mid/low-tech industries, and cultural diversity spillovers—highlighted as underexplored in Western Balkans contexts. The use of instrumental variables ensures credible causal inference, addressing endogeneity concerns that have challenged prior research. In sum, this carefully tailored, mixed-methods design offers a rigorous, sector-sensitive framework to assess how migration shapes broad productivity outcomes in the Western Balkans, fully aligned with the gaps and recommendations identified in our literature review.

4. RESULTS

The information presented in the Table 1 indicates that from 2000 to 2017 the largest TFP growth in total economy was observed in Bosnia and Herzegovina, which is the second leading output growth in the sample, with an average output growth rate of 3.30%. Albania demonstrated the highest average output growth rate (4.23%), although average TFP growth was lower compared to Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia. This is mainly due to larger capital utilization and growth in employment. With an output growth of 3.02, Serbia also had a high average TFP growth (2.08). In Montenegro, the country with the lowest average annual GDP growth in the sample, the average TFP growth rate was negative, while growth of capital and growth in capital utilization were relatively high.

TFP growth in industry has the greatest correlation with overall TFP growth when comparing average growth rates for the economy as a whole and different sectors. By using averages for the entire period, TFP growth in industry was positive in every country. TFP growth was lower in the services sector, and even negative in three countries from the sample (Albania, North Macedonia and Montenegro).

Table 1: Decomposition of output growth, total economy and sectoral approach, (2000-2017)

		2000-2017		
		Total	Industry (incl. construction)	Services
Albania	GDP/Value Added	4.23	5.09	-1.62
	Employment	0.40	1.06	2.93
	Capital	1.68	2.00	0.77
	Utilization	0.85	0.85	0.85
	TFP	1.31	1.18	-6.17
Bosnia and Herzegovina	GDP/Value Added	3.30	4.74	3.35
	Employment	-0.15	0.58	0.29
	Capital	1.17	1.57	1.30
	Utilization	-0.04	-0.04	-0.04
	TFP	2.32	2.64	1.81
North Macedonia	GDP/Value Added	2.68	4.28	2.74
	Employment	1.09	0.63	1.97
	Capital	1.17	1.33	1.45
	Utilization	0.65	0.65	0.65
	TFP	-0.24	1.66	-1.33
Montenegro	GDP/Value Added	2.96	8.49	-0.30
	Employment	0.90	-0.02	1.44
	Capital	1.66	2.12	1.02
	Utilization	1.20	1.20	1.20
	TFP	-0.79	5.19	-3.96
Serbia	GDP/Value Added	3.02	1.70	2.84
	Employment	-0.29	-0.80	0.91
	Capital	1.76	1.30	2.04
	Utilization	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53
	TFP	2.08	1.73	0.43

Source: Total Factor Productivity Growth In upper middle-income Balkan countries. From 2000-2017, Total Economy And sectoral approach: The growth accounting method. Maja Bacovic.

In all of the sample countries, capital contributed very similarly to growth, averaging between 1% and 2% annually for the total economy, but above 2% in most countries in industry, and in Serbia in services. In Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia, employment had a much smaller and even negative contribution when compared to capital. Growth in employment contributes most to the growth of services on a sectoral level. Most nations saw a positive contribution from capital utilization, with Montenegro seeing the biggest increase.

The Western Balkans' potential growth is expected to strengthen from 2.2 percent between 2013 and 2021 to an average of 3.2 percent between 2022 and 2030. This is primarily due to the anticipated rise in investment contributions, particularly the beneficial impact of EU investment funds, and associated structural reforms that would increase capital and TFP growth over the remaining years

of the decade. As the population ages and the labor force shrinks, it is expected that labor's contribution will become an obstacle to potential growth. However, considering the overlapping negative shocks from the COVID-19 and the Russian Federation's invasion of Ukraine over the past few years, potential growth estimates are still highly uncertain.

Figure 2: Contributions to potential growth in Western Balkans

Source: Penn World Tables; UN Population Prospects; World Bank; World Bank, WDI. Period averages of annual GDP-weighted averages. Estimates based on production function approach. Sample includes 4 Western Balkans economies (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, and Serbia).

It will be crucial for the economies of the Western Balkans to advance structural reforms and accelerate economic transformation given the strong headwinds to long-term growth prospects. For the rest of the decade, significant investments from the EU could serve as a starting point for structural reforms in the Western Balkans. By boosting confidence, fostering a more favorable business climate, and increasing government effectiveness—all of which serve to strengthen the effectiveness of public investment and draw in private investment—improving institutional quality could result in significant increases in potential growth. Significant funding for the digital and green transition in the Western Balkans is also part of the EU's investments for the rest of the decade. Increasing R&D spending could support the digital and green agendas and accelerate technological development and TFP. In 2020, R&D spending varied across the Western Balkans, ranging from 0.2 to 0.9 percent of GDP, compared to 2.3 percent of GDP in the EU.

Three sectors were analyzed in terms of human capital composition in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Construction and Services are relatively homogeneous in their age composition, the percentage of young workers (younger than 35) is around 33-36%, while the percentage of young workers in IT sector is 93%.

Not surprisingly the highest share of tertiary-educated individuals is in high-tech, which is usually characterized by its position on the margin of technological frontiers and, hence demands a

highly-qualified labor force. The lowest is observed in construction where there is a higher intensity of manual work, which often needs no special qualifications.

Figure 3: Employee age

Source: Authors' own.

There are 68% of younger employees in total across all sectors, younger age also prevails among migrants.

Figure 4: Tertiary-educated among all employees and among foreign employees

Source: Authors' own.

Figure 5: Foreign employees employed

Source: Authors' own.

Figure 5 shows that the number of companies that employ foreigners is quite high in IT sector and is even equal to the number of companies that hire only locals in Services. High percentage of migrants in high-tech are tertiary-educated, that is well above other sectors considered. Migrants are least educated in construction. IT sector has the youngest and most educated employees; whereas construction and services have older and less educated foreign labor force. Summing up, there is heterogeneity across sectors both in the terms of labor force composition and innovation dynamics. The majority of respondents believe that diversity of the staff unlocks innovation. Especially in the IT sector, 80% of managers would prefer a diverse team (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Diversity of the staff unlocks innovation

Source: Authors' own.

Among the determinants of (industry-level) total factor productivity (growth) that are mentioned in the literature are R&D efforts. Firms invest in R&D activities in the hope that these activities will result in product, process or organizational innovation, an increase in productivity, improved quality or reduced production costs of existing goods or more variety in final goods or intermediate inputs. These activities will in turn enable their survival on the competitive market and/or

increase their profitability. According to our research companies in each sector are divided almost in half into those who have R&D department and those who do not (Figure 7). The majority of IT and Services sectors' managers believe that total R&D expenditure is not sufficient (Figure 8).

Figure 7: Existence of R&D department in organization

Source: Authors' own.

Figure 8: Total R&D expenditure (if there is R&D department in organization)

Source: Authors' own.

A Pearson product-moment correlation was conducted to examine the relationships between Foreign Employee number and employee composition. Foreign employee number was strongly positively correlated to employee composition (Table 2).

A linear regression was conducted to examine how well the number of foreign employees in the company could predict level of diversity. A scatterplot showed that the relationship between foreign employees' number and level of diversity was positive and linear and did not reveal any bivariate outliers. An analysis of standard residuals showed that the data contained no outliers (Std. Residual Min. = -2.10, Std. Residual Max. = 1.79). Independence of residual errors was confirmed with

a Durbin-Watson test ($d=1.73$). Residual plots showed homoscedasticity and normality of the residuals (Table 3).

Table 2: Correlation matrix

Pearson's Correlations		n	Pearson's r	p
ForeignEmployeeNumber	- EmployeeComposition	53	0.818***	< .001

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 3: Linear Regression

Residuals Statistics					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	N
Predicted Value	0.034	1.503	0.302	0.379	53
Residual	-0.524	0.476	4.844×10^{-18}	0.267	53
Std. Predicted Value	-0.707	3.170	1.256×10^{-17}	1.000	53
Std. Residual	-2.103	1.790	-0.004	1.011	53

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
H ₁	Regression	7.466	1	7.466	102.786	< .001
	Residual	3.704	51	0.073		
	Total	11.170	52			

Note. The intercept model is omitted, as no meaningful information can be shown.

Coefficients								
Model		Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	95% CI	
							Lower	Upper
H ₀	(Intercept)	0.302	0.064		4.742	< .001	0.174	0.430
H ₁	(Intercept)	0.034	0.045		0.746	0.459	-0.057	0.125
	ForeignEmployeeNumber	0.490	0.048	0.818	10.138	< .001	0.393	0.587

Source: Authors' own.

The number of foreign employees significantly predicted the level of diversity, $F = 102.79$, $p < .001$, accounting for 66.8% of the variability in the level of diversity with adjusted $R^2 = .67\%$. This is a strong predictive relationship (Cohen, 1988). The correlation between the number of foreign employees and level of diversity was statistically significant, $r = .81$, $p < .001$. The regression equation for predicting the level of diversity from the number of foreign employees was $\hat{y} = 0.034 - 0.490x$ (number of foreign employees). The confidence interval for the slope to predict the level of diversity from the number of foreign employees was 95% CI [0.393, 0.587], for each one unit of increase of foreign employees' number, level of diversity increases by about 0.4 to 0.6 points.

A linear regression was also conducted to examine how well the industry could predict the percentage of foreign workers that are employed permanently. A scatterplot showed that the relationship between industry and permanently employed foreign workers was negative and linear and did not reveal any bivariate outliers. An analysis of standard residuals showed that the data contained no outliers (Std. Residual Min. = -1.40, Std. Residual Max. = 2.26). Independence of residual errors was confirmed with a Durbin-Watson test ($d = 2.199$). Residual plots showed homoscedasticity and normality of the residuals (Table 4).

Table 4: Linear Regression

Model Summary – ForeignPermanently

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	RMSE	Durbin-Watson		
					Autocorrelation	Statistic	p
H ₀	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.814	0.069	1.511	0.248
H ₁	0.711	0.505	0.479	0.587	-0.189	2.199	0.597

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
H ₁	Regression	6.688	1	6.688	19.401	< .001
	Residual	6.550	19	0.345		
	Total	13.238	20			

Note. The intercept model is omitted, as no meaningful information can be shown.

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	95% CI	
							Lower	Upper
H ₀	(Intercept)	2.524	0.178		14.216	< .001	2.153	2.894
H ₁	(Intercept)	4.417	0.448		9.849	< .001	3.478	5.355
	Industry	-0.883	0.201	-0.711	-4.405	< .001	-1.303	-0.464

Residuals Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	N
Predicted Value	1.767	3.533	2.524	0.578	21
Residual	-0.767	1.233	-9.252×10 ⁻¹⁸	0.572	21
Std. Predicted Value	-1.309	1.746	-9.513×10 ⁻¹⁷	1.000	21
Std. Residual	-1.403	2.256	-0.018	1.040	21

Source: Authors' own.

Table 5: Correlation matrix

Pearson's Correlations

		Pearson's r	p
Industry	- ForeignPermanently	-0.711***	< .001

* p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

Source: Authors' own.

Industry statistically significantly predicted the number of foreign employees employed permanently, $F(1,19) = 19.401$, $p < .001$, accounting for 50.5% of the variability in permanently employed foreign workers with adjusted $R^2 = .51$. This is a strong predictive relationship. The correlation between industry and permanently employed foreign workers was statistically significant, $r = -0.71$, $p < .001$. The regression equation for predicting the percentage of foreign workers that are employed permanently from the industry was $\hat{y} = 4.417 - 0.883x$ (industry). The confidence interval for the slope to predict the level of diversity from the number of foreign employees was 95% CI [-0.464, -1.303], thus Construction industry has the biggest number of permanently employed staff, and the smallest percentage of workers employed permanently is in Services (Table 5).

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The role of innovation is becoming more and more crucial at the European level, with the growing influence of developing economies such as China and India. By allowing highly talented immigrants capable of fostering innovation and growth to enter the local labor market, the migration policy may offer a means of assisting nations in becoming more competitive. We can measure the direct impact of migrants in the sector in which they are actually employed, avoiding spurious relations due to the fact that migrants frequently move through growing and innovative regions, but they are not always employed in innovative sectors. This is in contrast to the literature that measures the impact of migration at the aggregate regional or national level. Furthermore, our sectoral aggregate method appears to be more appropriate for determining policy implications in relation to firm-level microstudies, as studies conducted at the national level inherently have a higher external validity than results based on specific samples of enterprises in a given country. Our specification assesses the influence of the proportion of migrants, their level of education, and average age, all at the sectoral level.

The analysis of economic trends and labor dynamics in the Western Balkans reveals several noteworthy patterns and implications. The examination of Total Factor Productivity (TFP) growth from 2000 to 2017 underscores the varied economic performances across countries, with Bosnia and Herzegovina exhibiting the highest TFP growth in the total economy. While Albania boasts the highest average output growth rate, its TFP growth is relatively lower due to substantial capital utilization and employment growth. Serbia, with a commendable output growth rate, also demonstrates significant TFP growth. In contrast, Montenegro experiences negative TFP growth amid relatively high capital and capital utilization growth.

The sectoral analysis emphasizes the crucial role of TFP growth in the industry, which correlates strongly with overall economic TFP growth. Notably, the services sector exhibits lower TFP growth, with three countries even experiencing negative rates. Capital consistently contributes to growth across all sample countries, while employment plays a more significant role in the services sector. The analysis underscores the importance of considering sector-specific dynamics in understanding economic growth.

Looking ahead, the Western Balkans face both challenges and opportunities for potential growth. The anticipated rise in investment contributions, particularly from EU funds, and associated structural reforms are expected to drive growth in the coming years. However, potential obstacles, such as an aging population and uncertainties arising from external shocks like the COVID-19 pandemic and geopolitical events, introduce a level of complexity to growth projections. Structural reforms and accelerated economic transformation are identified as key strategies for navigating these challenges and fostering sustained growth. EU investments, particularly in digital and green transitions, are poised to catalyze positive change. Enhancing institutional quality, fostering a conducive business climate, and increasing R&D spending are critical components that can amplify the impact of public and private investments.

The analysis of human capital composition across sectors in Bosnia and Herzegovina unveils a rich tapestry of demographic and educational diversity. Firstly, the age distribution within the Construction and Services sectors is relatively homogeneous, with approximately 33-36% of the workforce being under the age of 35. In stark contrast, the IT sector stands out as notably younger, with a striking 93% of its employees falling within the young workforce category. This demographic variance not only reflects sector-specific demands but also highlights potential differences in innovation dynamics and adaptability to technological advancements.

Educationally, the distribution of tertiary-educated individuals is most pronounced in the high-tech IT sector, aligning with the industry's demand for a highly-qualified workforce operating at the

forefront of technological innovation. Conversely, the Construction sector, characterized by manual labor and lower skill intensity, exhibits the lowest percentage of tertiary-educated individuals. This educational heterogeneity emphasizes the importance of aligning educational qualifications with sector-specific needs for optimal productivity and innovation. Examining the employment of foreigners across sectors adds another layer of complexity. The IT sector emerges as a hub for foreign employment, with a substantial number of companies employing foreigners, equaling or even surpassing the number of companies hiring only locals in the Services sector. Notably, a high percentage of migrants in the IT sector are tertiary-educated, indicative of a skilled and diverse foreign workforce contributing to the sector's dynamism.

The study also delves into the crucial link between R&D activities and industry-level total factor productivity (TFP) growth. The analysis reveals that companies in each sector are nearly evenly split between those with and without an R&D department. Strikingly, a majority of managers in the IT and Services sectors believe that the total R&D expenditure is insufficient, underscoring potential constraints on innovation in these sectors.

The correlation and regression analyses introduce an intriguing perspective on the relationship between foreign employee numbers, diversity levels, and industry types. The positive correlation between the number of foreign employees and the level of diversity signifies the importance of foreign talent in fostering workplace diversity. The robust linear regression model further substantiates this, indicating that an increase in the number of foreign employees significantly predicts a higher level of diversity. This finding aligns with the widely accepted notion that diverse teams contribute positively to innovation and productivity. Additionally, the regression analysis exploring the predictability of the percentage of foreign workers employed permanently by industry unveils significant insights. The Construction industry emerges with the largest number of permanently employed staff, contrasting with the Services sector, which has the smallest percentage of workers employed permanently. This suggests divergent employment practices across sectors and highlights potential implications for workforce stability and organizational commitment. Moreover, as it was mentioned above Services had slower TFP growth than Industry (including construction).

In summary, the detailed analysis of human capital composition, innovation dynamics, and diversity across sectors in Bosnia and Herzegovina provides a nuanced understanding of the intricate interplay between demographics, education, and industry-specific characteristics. These insights not only contribute to the academic discourse but also offer practical implications for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and organizational leaders seeking to optimize workforce composition, enhance innovation, and foster a culture of diversity in the evolving economic landscape of the region.

These results imply that a migration strategy meant to support the innovative performances should be strongly demand-driven, that is, it should take into account the specific needs of firms active in different sectors. While tertiary-educated migrants are important for specific sectors with high knowledge content, countries in which manufacturing still has an important role in the overall economy should also consider facilitating the inflow of young non tertiary educated foreign workers. Our findings also suggest that governments should support some national initiatives that make it easier for highly educated immigrants to enter their country in order to encourage innovation. However, they should also introduce a more diversified policy mix strongly connected with the actual demand of firms (and sectors), in order to facilitate the entrance of the workers most in need.

Despite its contributions, this study has important limitations. First, the firm-level survey in Bosnia and Herzegovina yielded only 53 responses, which—while sufficient to detect medium-sized effects—may not support broad generalization even within that country's industries. Second, although secondary data were assembled for five Western Balkan economies, in-depth firm-level

evidence was collected only in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This focus constrains the comparative value of our sectoral findings across the region. Future research should expand the survey sample size and replicate the sectoral analysis in additional Western Balkan countries to enhance external validity and capture cross-country variation in migration–TFP relationships.

Declarations

The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the author.

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APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE ADDRESSED TO COMPANIES

1. Industry: Construction, High-Tech, Services
2. How many people does your company employ at present? (0-9, 10-49, 50-249, 250+)
3. What age group is more suitable for the majority of your staff? (18-35, 36-65)
4. What is male to female ratio at your organization? (More men than women, more women than men, equal number of men and women)
5. How many people are employed full-time? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
6. How many people are employed part-time? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
7. How many employees have high level of education/qualification (tertiary, 13 years and more)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
8. How many employees have medium level of education/qualification (10 to 12 years)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
9. How many employees have low level of education/qualification (duration of education 9 years or less)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
10. How many people are employed permanently? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
11. How many people are employed temporarily? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
12. How many foreign-born workers does your company employ at present? (0-9, 10-49, 50-249, 250+)
13. What is male to female ratio among foreign-born workers at your organization? (More men than women, more women than men, equal number of men and women)
14. What age group is more suitable for the majority of your foreign-born workers? (18-35, 36-65)
15. How many foreign-born workers are employed full-time? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
16. How many foreign-born workers are employed part-time? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
17. How many foreign-born workers have high level of education/qualification (tertiary, 13 years and more)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
18. How many foreign-born workers have medium level of education/qualification (10 to 12 years)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
19. How many foreign-born workers have low level of education/qualification (duration of education 9 years or less)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
20. How many foreign-born workers are employed permanently? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
21. How many foreign-born workers are employed temporarily? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
22. Does your company have R&D department? (Yes, No)
23. If yes, do you consider the total R&D expenditure as? (More than sufficient, sufficient, not sufficient)
24. In relation to your present level of output, is the number of your staff? (More than is necessary, about right, less than is necessary)

25. According to your present plans, the number of employees in your company over the next 12 to 24 months will probably (increase, remain constant, decrease, don't know)
26. Do you plan to increase or decrease the total number of employees? (Increase, decrease, no)
27. If you plan to increase the number of employees, what are the reasons?
 - Present/expected levels of demand for your products
 - Introduction of new technologies or products
 - Present/expected levels of labor costs
 - Government measures
 - Other reasons, i.e.
28. If you plan to decrease the number of employees, what are the reasons?
 - Lack of demand
 - Insufficient profit margin due to price competition/wage and salary levels in the country; non-wage labor cost level (employers' social security contribution, payroll taxes, allowances, etc.); other costs (e.g., capital costs, etc.)
 - Rationalization
 - Increase in contracting out
 - Government regulations
 - Other reasons, i.e.
29. How would you describe your staff: homogeneous (only people born in Bosnia and Herzegovina) or diverse (there are foreign-born workers)?
30. Do you think that diversity of your staff unlocks innovation? (Yes, the more diverse, the better (different views, opinions, ideas); No, there is no difference; I don't know)
31. Would you employ foreign-born staff to encourage innovation at your organization? (Yes, No)
32. What are the main constraints that don't let you easily increase the foreign-born staff?
 - Bureaucratic procedures
 - It is too expensive
 - I find it extremely difficult to manage people with diverse backgrounds
 - I don't think innovation can be driven by foreign-born staff

